

Expert evaluation

14 réponses

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Dataset 2 Evaluation

Question 1:

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For each intent i , do you consider the placement compliant with the service requirements and node capabilities?

Dataset 3 Evaluation

Question 2:

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For intents $i2$ to $i5$, which placement do you consider better?

Question 3:

 Copier

For intent *i6*, do you consider the placement produced by the **MILP solver** compliant with the service requirements and node capabilities?

14 réponses

Dataset 4 Evaluation

Here are the details of intents *i8* and *i31*:

```
{ "id": "i8", "description": "Detect wear or damage on conveyor belt.",  
  "services": ["s5"], "QoS": { "latency": 120, "bandwidth": 60, "weight": 7 },  
  "id": "i31", "description": "Detect wear or damage on gearbox teeth.",  
  "services": ["s5"], "QoS": { "latency": 120, "bandwidth": 60, "weight": 7 }
```

Model outputs:

LLM-based model:

- Intent i8: s5 → Node n12
- Intent i31: s5 → Node n12

MILP Solver:

No results provided

Question 5:

For intents *i8* and *i31*, do you consider the placement compliant with the service requirements and node capabilities?

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